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Securing Marine Renewable Energy Systems: Understanding Cyber-Physical Threats and Evaluating Consequences via Hardware-in-the-Loop

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Abstract

This paper addresses some of the cybersecurity challenges faced by marine renewable energy systems, particularly Marine Current Turbines, amid the global shift towards sustainable energy. It explores the cyber-physical threats these systems encounter, ranging from tampering with industrial control systems (ICS) that regulate turbine operations to falsifying sensor data and disrupting communication networks. A man-in-the-middle attack model specific to grid-integrated Marine Current Turbines is used, examining potential effects within the marine environment and the pivotal role of ICS. Through a hardware-in-the-loop (HIL) simulation of a grid-connected turbine, this study demonstrates the real-time impacts of such attacks on energy production and grid stability. This analysis highlights the urgent need for targeted detection and mitigation strategies to protect against cyber-physical threats, emphasizing the importance of securing ICS and fostering interdisciplinary collaboration among marine engineering, cybersecurity, and environmental science experts to enhance the resilience and reliability of marine renewable energy infrastructure.

Keywords: Marine Current Turbine; Hardware-In-Loop; Industrial Control System; Man-In-The-Middle

Main text

Nomenclature

Industrial Control System (ICS): Integrated hardware and software designed to monitor and control the operations of industrial processes and machinery.

Hardware-In-Loop (HIL): A testing method that integrates physical components into a simulated environment to validate and refine system performance.

Marine Current Turbine (MCT): a renewable energy device that harnesses the kinetic energy of marine currents, including ocean, tidal, and river currents, to generate electricity.

1.1. Introduction

The global need for reliable and uninterrupted power has become increasingly critical, with incidents such as the 2006 European blackout highlighting the need for continuous improvements on the infrastructure's reliability, security, and optimization [1]. In response, the energy sector is transitioning towards more modernized designs, integrating advanced systems such as SCADA and other forms of information and operational technology (IT/OT) systems [2]. Furthermore, with electricity demand projected to grow by over 13.3 TWh/yr from 2017 to 2040 [3], the deployment of alternative renewable energy sources, such as Marine Renewable Energy (MRE) systems, is on the rise. Marine Current Turbines (MCTs), in particular, are noted for their consistent and weather-independent energy production. Additionally, the integration of MRE systems with the blue economy is proving beneficial for offshore

operations, including ocean observation systems, desalination plants, and remote microgrids like those on the island of Ta'u [2]. However, the isolated operational environments of MRE systems like MCTs make them vulnerable targets for adversaries, due to their remote and difficult to maintain locations.

From 2018 to 2020, the World Economic Forum consistently ranked cyberattacks on critical infrastructure among the top five global risks [4, 5, 6]. Additionally, cyberattacks targeting Industrial Control Systems (ICS) are becoming increasingly prevalent [7], with notorious attacks such as Stuxnet and Industroyer serving as prime examples [8]. The rising threat of cyberattacks, combined with the development of isolated systems such as MCTs and other MREs, poses significant risks to the blue economy energy sector, as well as small island/coastal communities, and grid-connected microgrids. Major organizations like the Pacific Northwest National Laboratory (PNNL) have initiated efforts to identify major cybersecurity threats to MRE systems and develop methods to evaluate the risk of attacks based on the deployed system [3]. However, this escalating vulnerability underscores the need for comprehensive and adaptive cybersecurity measures to protect these critical energy infrastructures from potential threats.

Understanding the impact of cyber-attacks on MRE systems is crucial for devising effective detection and mitigation strategies. Typically, attack analysis and mitigation testing are conducted through simulations [9, 10, 11], which can introduce complexities and inaccuracies, especially when modeling mechanical hardware. Hardware-in-the-loop (HIL) simulations mitigate these challenges by integrating physical hardware into the simulation loop, enhancing accuracy and emulating real-world conditions. For instance, research [12] compares the effects of a wind turbine cyber-attack with and without HIL components revealing that incorporating HIL can decrease resilience under more realistic conditions, thus validating the added accuracy provided by real hardware. Moreover, industrial-grade HIL testbeds have been utilized for precise testing and certification of large-scale components, as demonstrated in studies like [13], where an industrial-sized HIL testbed was employed for the electrical certification of wind turbine nacelles. Initially utilized for design assessment and control verification, HIL also proved invaluable for accurately analyzing cyber-attacks, as evidenced by [12, 14]. Beyond analysis, HIL is recognized as a cost-effective and precise method for developing and testing new detection and mitigation strategies, as emphasized in [15]. This study aims to evaluate the accuracy of analyzing targeted cyber-attacks on a HIL MCT testbed, furthering the research and development of cybersecurity testing in MREs.

1.2. Testbed Description

The HIL MCT testbed used in this study is from [16] where an OPAL-RT 4510 HIL simulator is used to integrate a 2.2 kW dynamometer with a microgrid simulation and ocean environment. The dynamometer acts as the MCT whilst the ocean environment, microgrid, and a blade-pitch controller are simulated in MATLAB Simulink. The torque feedback from the MCT is scaled to imitate a 20 m rotor diameter turbine and is used as an input to the asynchronous generator within the microgrid simulation. The HIL test bed and communication flow can be seen in Fig. 1.

Figure 1: Hardware-in-the-Loop communication and testbed

The dynamometer testbed comprises two AC induction motors coupled together via direct drive with zero backlash couplings and a torque cell for precise torque measurements. The prime mover is a 2 HP, 1800 RPM induction motor controlled by a Variable Frequency Drive (VFD) set to torque control, while the motor under test (MUT) is a 3 HP, 1800 RPM inverter-duty motor controlled by a VFD set to speed control, acting as an active generator load. The setup

includes dual quadrature encoders for speed feedback and a torque cell to communicate torque information back to the Opal-RT system, which drives the asynchronous generator within the Simulink microgrid model in Fig. 2.

The microgrid model, adapted from [17] for HIL of an MCT, includes a 50 kW consumer load and a variable secondary load of 0 to 446.25 kW to manage excess power. The grid operates using a 480 V, 275 kVA asynchronous generator and a 480 V, 300 kVA diesel-driven synchronous machine, which manages reactive power as a synchronous condenser during over-generation. A phase-locked loop discrete frequency controller maintains a consistent grid frequency of 60 Hz, while a blade pitch controller is implemented on the MCT in region 3 to curb over generation for high marine current velocities. During normal operation, the MCT in this model generates approximately 160 kW of power. For this specific grid configuration, the MCT's contribution is substantial, and a reduction in output below 70 kW can cause the synchronous condenser to try to compensate until it reaches its limit of 300 kVA and ultimately crashes. This threshold represents a critical point at which the system becomes unable to maintain grid stability.

Figure 2: Microgrid Simulink Model

1.3. Attack Scenario

Adversaries can gain initial access to a system's network through various methods, such as spear phishing, remote service intrusion, wireless compromise [8], or physical tactics like fiber optic tapping [18]. Once inside the network, the system is exposed to a range of attacks. ICSs are especially vulnerable to specific cyber threats. These include SQL injection, where attackers exploit a system's database using malicious SQL statements, and cross-site scripting (XSS), which targets the software interfaces managing industrial equipment. Other common attack vectors include denial of service (DoS) attacks that disrupt service availability and man-in-the-middle (MITM) attacks, which intercept and alter communication between systems. These methods can lead to significant disruptions, data theft, or even physical damage to infrastructure.

According to Verizon's data investigation report [19], one of the most common types of security attacks is MITM. Unlike attacks that require escalated privileges, MITM attacks intercept and alter communication without needing administrative access, making intrusion easier. The attacks observed in this experiment target an MCT's ICS and are based on the Manipulation of Control (T0831) and Manipulation of View (T0832) attacks from the MITRE database [8]. It is assumed that the attacker has knowledge of the system and can view and manipulate control system parameters and sensor data via a local area network (LAN) as shown in Fig. 3. In this scenario, a MITM attack is used to manipulate control parameter signals going into a PID controller of the turbine. This is combined with False Data Injection (FDI) attacks to deceive grid sensors into interpreting compromised data as normal operation, as discussed in [18]. The FDI attack is executed by injecting an attack vector a into the measurement vector z , creating a compromised measurement z' as follows:

$$z' = z + a \quad (1)$$

By carefully crafting and injecting false data, the attacker can manipulate sensor readings and control commands, causing the grid to react to fabricated conditions and deceive grid operators. This deception allows the attacker to create instability or damage while avoiding detection, as compromised measurements blend seamlessly with legitimate data.

Figure 3: General MITM attack scenario for the HIL MCT microgrid setup under test

1.4. Results

1.4.1. Case 1: Oscillating Blade Pitch

The first investigated attack involves creating oscillations in the blade pitch controller by manipulating the P, I, and D parameters to create instability in the output. These values oscillate from an extreme low to an extreme high which causes the blade-pitch of the rotor to rapidly change, affecting the mechanical torque being produced. This has effects on both the mechanical hardware of the turbine and the stability of the grid. As mentioned in [20], high frequency oscillations on the blade-pitch can cause premature wear to hardware such as the clutch, gearbox, and brakes. Additionally, these oscillations directly affect the microgrid by causing high magnitude fluctuations in both the frequency and power output, causing distortions which lead to decreased efficiency.

Figure 4: (a) The frequency and blade-pitch under oscillatory attack (b) The generator and load response to attack

In Fig. 4, the attack is executed at 19 s, where oscillations in blade pitch can be observed. The frequency maintains oscillations consistent with the blade pitch, while MCT is also directly affected as shown in Fig. 4b, possibly causing damage to the rotor and creating instability at the synchronous condenser and secondary load. The grid observations are seen to be operating normally, making the attack stealthier. The power quality is affected during this attack, which can be seen by analyzing the Total Harmonic Distortion (THD) as shown in Fig. 5, where the THD is shown to have a drastic increase. IEEE 519 defines the safe limits of THD on lines being dependent on both the voltage and current supplied [21]. Prior to the attack, the THD on the output current of the generator is shown to be -93.46 dB (0.002%) as shown in Fig. 5a. When the attack is implemented, many inter-harmonics are introduced into the frequency spectrum as shown in Fig. 5b which causes the THD to jump drastically to -70.27 dB (0.03%) showing a 15x increase. These percentages are low due to the microgrid simulation using a static load rather than a dynamic one. However, the amount of power distributed into unwanted frequencies observed in Fig. 5b highlights how these oscillations increase THD by an order of magnitude.

Figure 5: (a) Total Harmonic distortion without attack; (b) Total harmonic distortion with attack

1.4.2. Case 2: Decreasing Power Production

The second type of attack involves spoofing the blade-pitch controller's input to erroneously signal an excess generation of power. As a result, the PID controller adjusts the blade pitch upwards while operating in region 2 of the turbine's power curve, leading to reduced efficiency and, in some instances, insufficient generation of power at the asynchronous generator. This shortfall in power generation causes the synchronous condenser to try to compensate; however, if it cannot produce enough power, the grid may collapse due to undervoltage.

Figure 6: (a) Blade pitch and frequency response; (b) Grid power response to attack

As shown in Fig. 6a, the attack is executed at 12 s, leading to an increase in blade pitch from 0° to 12° . This adjustment significantly reduces the mechanical torque on the rotor, resulting in insufficient power generation by the asynchronous generator. Following the attack's onset, the MCT power, shown in Fig. 6b, decreased sharply from 160 kW to about 48 kW and then gradually reduced, ultimately crashing. As the MCT's power output gradually decreases, the synchronous condenser attempts to compensate by generating increasing amounts of power until it reaches its 300 kVA limit and crashes, causing the entire grid to collapse. Additionally, at the beginning of the attack the frequency is shown to exponentially decrease until crashing.

1.5. Conclusion

This study demonstrated the impact of cyber-physical attacks on the operational integrity of a microgrid connected to an MCT. The hardware-in-the-loop (HIL) simulation, integrated with Simulink, provided a robust platform for evaluating the resilience of marine energy systems against sophisticated attack vectors. Specifically, the manipulation of the control system and the injection of false data (FDI) attacks revealed critical vulnerabilities that can lead to severe disruptions in grid operations. These attacks caused erroneous power generation data, leading to instability in power distribution and potential failures in energy management systems. The deceptive nature of FDI attacks, which masked the true state of the system, further underscored the need for advanced detection and mitigation strategies.

The application of HIL testing proved invaluable in this context. It allowed for realistic and repeatable testing scenarios without the associated risks and costs of conducting experiments in the marine environment. The ability to simulate real-world conditions and introduce controlled cyber-physical attacks provided insight into the dynamic behavior of the microgrid under compromised conditions. The negative impacts of cyber-physical attacks on grid operations highlight the critical need for enhanced security measures in marine energy systems. HIL testing emerges as a tool for advancing the reliability and security of power systems, enabling researchers and engineers to conduct thorough and safe evaluations before deploying technologies in challenging marine environments.

While this study focuses on a single MCT microgrid, the findings can also be extended to larger, grid-connected MCT arrays. However, if a cyber-attack targets only a single MCT in a larger array, the consequences for the overall grid would likely be minimal since other turbines would continue generating power. However, the compromised turbine could experience significant operational issues, leading to potential mechanical damage or reduced efficiency. Conversely, a more complex, coordinated attack targeting the entire MCT array would pose major risks both to the turbines and the grid. Such an attack could cause widespread instability by disrupting the array's collective energy contribution, leading to grid-level consequences that are far more severe than those observed in a microgrid scenario. This highlights the need for robust, system-wide cybersecurity measures in larger, grid-connected deployments of MCTs.

Future work will concentrate on creating a data-driven attack detection method and an attack-resilient fault-tolerant controller for mitigation. These methods will be tested within the HIL configuration to validate its effectiveness and reliability in detecting cyber threats on MRE systems and isolated microgrids.

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